

INDUSTRIAL ACTION AND EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN NIGERIA A CASE STUDY OF FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OTUOKE, BAYELSA STATE

¹Bodmas Tounbra Felix

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Abstract

The study examined industrial action and employee productivity in public universities. The study seeks how general strike affects employee productivity, it seeks how wildcat strike affects employee productivity, and it explore how economic strike affects employee productivity. The study adopted a descriptive research design targeting. The study collected primary data using a semi structured questionnaire. The collected data was analyzed using multiple regression with the aid of statistical package for social sciences. The result of our regression shows general strike has a positive coefficient of 0.532 and a P-value 0.000, wildcat strike has a positive coefficient of .681 and a P-value of 0.000, economic strike has a positive coefficient of .653 and a P-value of 0.000. The study concludes that failure by government to honour promises or agreement is a contributing factor to strike action in Nigeria. The study therefore recommends that the government must fulfil promises or agreements that were made in order to avoid or reduce strike action in universities.

INTRODUCTION

There is the need for organizations to see to the satisfaction of their employees, due to the crucial role they tend to play. This may be done by adopting several measures, a clear example being the use of enhanced industrial relations mechanism. Industrial relations consolidate the relationship between employees and management, and also play a critical role in resolving employee dissatisfaction. Industrial relations covers three distinct areas: relations between a manager and individual employees, collective relations between employers and labour (trade) unions, and the role of government in the regulation of these relationships (Branham, 2015).

Strikes are the most significant aspect of industrial conflict. Strike is defined as the temporary stoppage of work in the pursuance of grievance or demand. In practice however, it has been difficult to separate strike from other forms of expression of industrial dispute as employer lock out workers and workers themselves embark on strike action. It is more useful to view both phenomena as part and parcel of the conflict situation, not as opposite. Rarely does a strike occur over a single issue for an obvious cause may be linked with several other issues that not immediately apparent to the observation that have caused dissatisfaction because solutions to

¹Department of Business Administration, Federal University Otuoke

them have been long in coming. The actual occurrence of strike depends on several factors including prevailing circumstances (Adetiba, 2012).

The education sub-sector especially tertiary institutions in Nigeria have witnessed in recent time incessant closures due to industrial actions. The effect of these repeated closures of schools and academic programs on students' learning effectiveness can better be imagined than described. Tertiary education in Nigeria has thus suffered tremendous setbacks as a result of industrial actions by both the academic (ASUU) and the non-academic staffs. This has always subjected the students to pitiable conditions, disrupting academic programs, giving students' undeserved extension in their study years, poor students' concentration on academic programs and poor lecturer-student relationships amongst others. Consequently, students' academic performance has comparatively become so low while various forms of examination malpractice are on the increase (Olugbenga, 2011).

University worldwide is regarded as the citadel of learning, the fountain of intellectual development and a ground for the production of leaders of tomorrow. All over the world investment in University education is a critical component of national development effort (Olugbenga, 2011). The main union whose incessant industrial action takes a heavy toll on the academic performance of the students is the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU). The union was formed in 1978, a successor to the Nigerian Association of University Teachers formed in 1965 and covering academic staff in the University of Ibadan, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, University of Ife and University of Lagos. In the 80's, the union was active in its struggles against the military regime. In 1988 the union organized a National industrial action to obtain fair wages and university autonomy. As a result, the ASUU was proscribed on August 7, 1988 and all its property seized. Often times, these incessant agitations by ASUU usually triggers industrial action by sister associations such as NASU, SSANU etc. (Fajana, 2000). These action affects employee productivity.

Employee productivity is a term typical to the Human Resource field where employee performance can refer to the ability of employees to achieve organizational goals more effectively and efficiently. It involves all aspects which directly or indirectly affect and relate to the work of the employees. For performance to be effective, employers should recognize the regiment desires and needs of the employees. Koontz, H. (2018) posits that the ways in which employee performance can be increased include; proper incentive systems which may be financial or nonfinancial. Financial incentives include; salaries, allowances, overtime payment, bonus and wages, while non-financial incentives include; promotion, medical allowance, training, transport, subsidized housing and meals. This should be after identifying the needs and desires of employees that can be satisfied hence increased performance.

Statement of the Problem

The demand of ASUU and other industrial unions in the Nigerian Universities is that government should fulfill an agreement it reached with them in 2009 on how to save the nation's universities from collapse. On the other hand, government is proposing a piecemeal selective approach. There is no doubt that education is too vital to the survival of any nation that it should be treated as a subject beyond politics or evasive polemics. It is not deniable that Nigeria is presently not doing enough, by world standards, in the funding of her children's education. As far as the government is concerned, there are other competing items for the limited funds available and government is not doing enough in the infrastructural development of the Nigerian Universities. Selala (2014) also suggests that strike action has a varied and wide-ranging effect on employment relationships. The occurrence of strikes in the public universities in Nigeria is very alarming and if serious action is not taken, the education system in the country will suffer dire consequences. It appears that the government, university management and other stakeholders have done little to resolve strikes in the country. Despite the numerous strike actions that took place in Nigerian public universities, little research has been done to investigate the causes of the strikes and possibly to provide recommendations to address or reduce the

occurrences of these strikes. It is against this background that this study seeks to investigate the impact of strike action on employee productivity in Nigerian public tertiary institution.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this study is to examine industrial action and employee productivity in the Nigeria tertiary institutions. The specific objectives are;

1. To examine the effect of general strike on employee productivity in Federal University Otuoke
 2. To explore the effect of wildcat strike on employee productivity in Federal University Otuoke
- To determine the impact of economic strike on employee productivity in Federal University Otuoke

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were stated in the null form

H01: there is no significant relationship between general strike and employee productivity in Federal University Otuoke

H02: there is no significant relationship between wildcat and employee productivity in Federal University Otuoke

H03: there is no significant relationship between economic strike and employee productivity in Federal University Otuoke

LITERATURE REVIEW

Strike Action

Generally, strike action has been referred to as the refusal of employees to work due to unresolved grievances, with the aim of enforcing their socio-economic demands. The term strike has been defined in several ways by international and local researchers (Ahmed, &Levy, 2011). This explains the fact that the meaning of strike action varies from one researcher to another. The following are some definitions and explanations of the term “strike action”:

Venter and Levy (2011), posit strike is the partial or complete concerted refusal to work, or the retardation or obstruction of work, by persons who are or have been employed by the same employer or by different employers, for the purpose of remedying a grievance or solving a dispute in respect of any matter of mutual interest between employer and employee, and every reference to work in this definition includes overtime work, whether it is voluntary or compulsory.

Venter and Levy (2011), posits the definition of strike action as set out in the LRA includes concerted action that amounts to both a complete stoppage of work and retardation in the workplace. Venter and Levy (2014) suggest that the above definition has three main elements. The first element is that a strike must constitute either a complete cessation of work or retardation of work process, hence incorporating go-slows, work-to-rule and the like. The second element in the definition is that the said action must be concerted. However, the authors argue that a cessation or retardation of the work process by one individual does not amount to strike action. Venter and Levy (2014), posits that the final element, is that a strike action can be embarked only in furtherance of a demand.

Grogan (2014) also ascribes to the definition offered by the LRA. The author argues that s64 of the LRA legitimises industrial action by granting workers the right to strike and the employers the right to lockout. Grogan (2014), states that, by common law, workers who embark on industrial action would be in breach of contract due to fact that they may not be able to perform their duties and therefore they could be dismissed by their employers. On the other hand, the employer would be breaching employment contracts if he/she prevented the employees from entering the workplace to carry out their duties. However, the new LRA allows both the employee and employer the right to strike and to lockout.

Bendix (2015), a strike may be broadly defined as a “a temporary, collective withholding of labour, its objective being to stop or impede the continuation of business and thereby to oblige the employer to take

notice of the employee demands". Bendix (2015) further adds that the fact that strike is a temporary measure is important. The author argues that workers embark upon industrial action to temporarily withhold their services from the employer in order to force the employer to negotiate with them.

Seniwoliba (2013), strike is any action taken by two or more workers acting in concert, which is intended by them to restrict in any way the service they normally provide to the employer or diminish the output of such service with a view to applying coercive pressure upon the employer and includes sympathy strike and those activities commonly called a work-to-rule, a goslow or a sit down strike.

The above definition by GLA also includes certain key words, as in the case of the LRA. Firstly, a strike action must be any action that is taken by two or more workers acting in concert. This clarifies the fact that the retardation of the work process by an individual does not in any way constitute a strike action. Secondly, the said action must be intended by employees to restrict the service they normally provide to the employer or diminish the output of such service. Thirdly, the action must include applying coercive pressure upon the employer. This may include sympathy strikes. Finally, the activities of the strike action may include a work-to-rule, a go-slow or a sit-down. The key elements in the definition offered by GLA can also be found in the LRA definition.

IgeAkindele (2014), a strike is the medium through which workers refuse to perform their work due to disagreement with their employer(s) over conditions of work. The author argues that there are two kinds of strikes that workers and their trade unions can embark on, namely, internal and nationwide. The internal strikes take place within the organisation while the nationwide strike involves many institutions across the country withdrawing their services. A careful look at this definition suggests that there are some technical gaps in it. Firstly, the definition of strike action is limited to employees of the primary employer. Thus it fails to make reference to secondary employers or sympathy strikes as contained in the definitions offered by the LRA and GLA. Furthermore, this definition by IgeAkindele (2014) falls short of mentioning what constitutes either a complete cessation of work or the refusal to work. Unlike the definitions of LRA and GLA, no reference is made to activities such as a work-to-rule, a go-slow or a sit-down strike. Although the definition by IgeAkindele (2014) gives a clear picture of what a strike action is, it cannot stand the test of time because of its technical gaps.

Edinyang and Ubi (2013) also define strike action as a deliberate stoppage of work by workers which is intended to put more pressure on the employer to satisfy their demands. The definition by these authors suggests that strike is stoppage of work by employees with the view to enforce their socio-economic demands. The definition by Edinyang and Ubi (2013) is similar to that of IgeAkindele (2014). Thus, the two definitions emphasise stoppage of work by workers or employers. Edinyang and Ubi's (2013) definition also contains key words such as: stoppage of work by workers and putting pressure on the employer to accede to their demands. This has a conceptual meaning but it also has some technical gaps. To begin with, the definition does not include secondary or sympathy strikes. By implication, it means that the definition is limited in scope to only the employees of the primary employer(s). In addition, the definition falls short, as it fails to incorporate actions such as go-slows, work-to-rule and sit-down.

Ahmed (2014), strike is a deliberate stoppage of work by workers in order to put pressure on their employer to accede to their demands". A critical look at this definition suggests that it falls in line with the definitions provided by Akindele (2014) and Edinyang and Ubi (2013). The definition by Ahmed (2014) also has two key elements. The first element is work stoppage and the second one is the employer acceding to the demands of the workers. From the authors' point of view, any action taken by workers in the form of work stoppage in furtherance of a demand is called "strike action". A careful scrutiny of the definition provided by Ahmed (2014) reveals that it shows conceptual understanding but lacks some legal technicalities, as seen in the first two definitions above. From the above discussion, strike can be defined by the researcher as any deliberate

attempt by workers to restrict the services they provide to the employer or to abandon their work in order to exert strong influence on their employer(s) to meet their demands.

Wildcat strike

Wildcat strike is one of the most popular types of strike action often embarked upon by workers worldwide. A wildcat strike is normally regarded as a fast, sudden and unapproved type of work stoppage. It is often regarded as an unapproved or unauthorised type of work stoppage because the union leaders are not in support of it (Bendix, 2015). Odeku (2014), is of the opinion that wildcat strikes arise as a result of 'fractional bargaining' by some specific subgroups of workers to have their own interest satisfied by the employer. Researchers (Adaviele, 2015; Clark, 2012) have argued that a wildcat strike is often masterminded by a subgroup of workers who are not satisfied with the collective bargaining procedures. In law, this type of strike is regarded as unprotected or illegal.

Nel (2012) also support the views of the above authors that a wildcat strike is a sudden and unauthorised work stoppage, with no notice to the employer. The purpose is to surprise the employer. This strike can result in absolute chaos of violence because usually there is no negotiation that takes place between the parties. Nel (2013), states that wildcat strikes often arise as a result of perceived unfair dismissal or unresolved disputes. Bendix (2015) also expresses the similar view that wildcat strikes occur without any prior warning. This type of strike is unprotected because it does not follow the laid down regulations by the LRA & GLA.

For instance, the 2012 Marikana strike that took place in South Africa is an example of a wildcat strike (Odeku, 2014). Similarly, in Ghana, a similar strike took place in March 2015 where a group of opposition parties went on strike in demand for a new voter register for the upcoming 2016 elections. Violence broke out between the police personnel and the strikers and this led to the injuries of some of the strikers.

Economic strike

Economic strike is one of the popular worldwide strikes which workers usually embark upon. In South Africa, Nigeria and Ghana, it is a form of common strike among workers (Adaviele, 2015; Bendix, 2015; Seniwoliba, 2013). Bendix (2015) is of the view that an economic strike arises due to the refusal or failure by employers to meet the demands of workers related to wages and other economic issues namely: benefits and working conditions.

Nelet *al.* (2013), an economic strike occurs as a result of the demands that pertain to wages, fringe benefits or any other matter of an economic nature regarding the interest of workers. Workers usually initiate this strike with the view to putting pressure on the employer in order to enforce their economic demands, for instance, an increase in wages, salaries and bonuses. Employees agitate for an increase in their wages and salaries, allowances, bonuses, and other entitlements, like an increase in annual leave, privilege leave and casual leave (Odeku, 2014). Clark (2012) also expresses the similar view that an economic strike is the most common and popular form of strike that workers frequently embark upon worldwide.

For instance, during 2013, the University Teachers Association of Ghana (UTAG) went on economic strike in an attempt to put pressure on the government to pay their research allowances, bonuses and salaries (Seniwoliba, 2013). Similarly, in South Africa, "in August 2013, technicians from the South African Transport and Allied Workers Union (SATAWU) went on economic strike regarding the refusal of South African Airways to add a 0.4% once off payment to their offer of 6.5%" (Murwirapachena&Sibanda, 2014, p.555). In addition, in September 2013, approximately 70, 000 petrol attendants and vehicle industry workers, mainly members of the National Union of Mine Workers of South Africa (NUMSA), went on a three day strike in demand for a 12.5% annual increase in wages and salaries. The above scenarios support the fact that economic strike is the most common type of strike that workers in Ghana, Nigeria and South Africa embark upon.

General strikes

A general strike also falls within the categories of strike. Odeku (2014), opines that this form of strike is usually embarked upon by all the registered trade unions in a country to enforce demands common to all the employees or workers across the country. A general strike is most often planned to exert political pressure on the ruling government rather than on any single employer. General strike is an extension of sympathy strikes by all the trade unions to express their concerns. For example, In South Africa, the 1992 Rand Rebellion is a classic example of general strike. Another example of a general strike is in 1948 in Ghana when several pro-independence politicians were arrested in a struggle for freedom. The arrest of these pro-independence politicians led to a nationwide strike action by the Trade Union Congress (TUC) and this resulted in the release of the politicians. Similarly, in 2014, all registered trade unions in Ghana went on a nationwide strike in protest against poor conditions of service in the country (Adeniji, 2015).

International Labour Organisation [ILO] an overview on the right to strike

The ILO is a special institution of the United Nations that engages in labour matters (Venter & Levy, 2014). It has its head office in Geneva, Switzerland. It is responsible for hosting annual International Labour Conferences in Geneva in June every year. The ILO remains very important for employment relations due to the fact that it focuses on quality employment relations across the globe. It ensures that Conventions and Recommendations are crafted and adopted by a majority decision during the conference. The core mandates of the ILO include: “formulating and supervising international labour standards in the form of conventions and recommendations, setting minimum standards of basic labour rights; freedom of association, the right to organise, collective bargaining, abolition of forced labour, equality of opportunity and treatment and other standards regulating conditions across the entire spectrum of work-related issues” (Venter & Levy, 2014).

Venter and Levy (2014), posits that the ILO aims at ensuring that labour standards are respected in practice as well as in principle while working with all its member states. It also ensures that all its member states comply with the minimum labour standards. However, failure of any of its member states to adopt human conditions of labour is an obstacle in the way of other nations which desire to improve the conditions in their countries. The primary goal of the ILO today is to promote opportunities for women and men to obtain decent and productive work, in conditions of freedom, equity, security and human dignity” (Venter & Levy, 2014).

Venter and Levy (2014), posits that the ILO has four main strategic objectives namely: to promote and realise standards and fundamental principles and rights at work; to create greater opportunities for women and men to obtain decent employment and income; to enhance the coverage and effectiveness of social protection for all and to strengthen tripartism and social dialogue.

Ahmed (2014), states that the ILO has a number of Conventions which include the Freedom of Association and the Right to Organise Convention No 87 of 1948, the Right to Organise and Collective Bargaining Convention No.98 of 1949, Discrimination (Employment and Occupational) Convention, No. 111 of 1958, Equality of Treatment (Social Security) Convention, No. 118 of 1962, Vocational Rehabilitation (Disabled) Recommendation, No. 99 of 1955, Unemployment Convention, No. 168 of 1988. However, Freedom of Association and the Right to Organise Convention No 87 of 1948, The Right to Organise and Collective Bargaining Convention No.98 of 1949 are the main ILO Conventions that support this study.

Ahmed (2014) contends that among these Conventions the ILO has two Conventions which recognise that the right to strike is an intrinsic corollary to the right to organise and a fundamental right of every worker and their organisation to collective bargaining. Rapatsa and Matloga (2014) also argue that the right to strike emanates from international instruments. Rapatsa and Matloga (2014), states that strike is recognised worldwide as a human right. The authors further state that Article 18(1)(d) of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) requires every nation who is a member of the ILO to covenant, to promote,

protect and respect the right to strike, provided this right is exercised in accordance with the laws of the land or the country.

The ILO through the recommendations made by the Committee of Freedom of Association (CFA) and Committee of Experts on Application of Conventions and Recommendations has recognised the right to strike as one of the avenues where workers and their trade unions can advance their economic and social interests. The Committee recommended that the right to strike is a right which workers and their organisations are entitled to (Ahmed, 2014).

As indicated above, there are two ILO Conventions that recognise the right to strike namely: Freedom of Association and the Right to Organise Convention No 87 of 1948 and Right to Organise and Collective Bargaining Convention No. 98 of 1949' (Deacon, 2014; La Hovary, 2013; Matee, 2014; Rapatsa&Matloga, 2014). The ILO's Committee of Experts on the Application and Recommendation are of the view that these Conventions give rise to the workers' right to strike.

Ahmed (2014), Article 3 of the ILO Convention No.87of 1948 recognises the right of trade unions and employer organisations to organise their activities and formulate programmes that will help them to promote their socio-economic interests. Mbah and Ikemefuna (2011) also argue that Convention No.87 of 1948 is fundamental to the exercise of collective labour rights by workers' associations. Ahmed (2014) emphasises that the Committee on Freedom of Association has given full recognition to strike action as a right and not a mere social act and it has also made it states that the right to strike is a right that workers and their trade unions or associations may exercise. Article 3(1) of this Convention encourages workers to form and join associations of their choice without any previous authorisation. In addition, it states that workers have the right to draw up their own constitutions and rules and to elect their own representatives (Malik, 2014).

The Right to Organise and Collective Bargaining Convention No.98 of 1949 is another instrument that recognises workers' right to strike (Ahmed, 2014; Odeku, 2014). Ahmed (2014), opines that the protection of the right to strike within Convention 87 is enhanced in practice by the protection contained in Convention 98. The Convention protects the right of workers to exercise their right to organise, free from anti-union discrimination. The Committee of Experts considers that without Convention 98, the guarantees set out in Convention 87 may be rendered nugatory (Ahmed, 2014).

Rapatsa and Matloga (2014), states that the protection of workers and their associations against acts of anti-union discrimination constitutes the most important aspect of freedom of association. Such an act may lead to the denial of guarantees set out in Convention No.87 of 1948. Odeku (2014), opines that the ILO Freedom of Association Conventions implement the principles of freedom of association through voluntary collective bargaining as specified in the Article 4 of Convention No.98.

Conceptual Framework

Conceptual Framework (2026)

Review of Related Theories

Kaufman (2010) posits that the s164 (1) provides that when any labour dispute is referred to compulsory arbitration with regard to ss160-162, the National Labour Commission shall constitute the arbitrator and shall serve notice on all the parties: (a) stating the fact of the case and in its views the issues that are not addressed; and (b) seeking from all the parties concerned information as to whether they agree to the issues. Section 164(2) also states that the National Labour Commission shall, resolve the dispute by compulsory arbitration within fourteen days of having served notice on all the parties to the dispute. Section 144(3) states that there shall be three panels who shall serve as arbitrators and also one representative from government, the trade union concerned and the employer’s association. Seniwoliba (2013) asserts that section 164(4) emphasises that the final decisions by the majority of the arbitrators shall form the basis of the arbitration award in a compulsory arbitration and this shall be binding on all the parties to the dispute.

Oloyede (2013) in his research work investigated the effect of strike action on the academic performance of students in some selected secondary school. To accomplish the objectives of this research, a questionnaire was drawn for one hundred and fifty students selected in the area of study. The finding of this research revealed that: strikes is caused by irregularities of teachers of salary, indiscipline of students in various schools, lack of dialogue between Government and Nigerian Union of teachers. All these result to strike actions, the effect of strike actions is usually decrease in performance of students’ academic in secondary school, in the year that are strike free. This study identified the fact that persistent strike leads to low moral in both students and teachers. The following recommendations and suggestions according to the research, if taken will reduce or totally eliminate strike. Attractive remuneration, adequate financing, Adherence to collective bargaining, provision of adequate education facilities and infrastructure that will enhance learning, the use of dialogue in resolving conflicts.

METHODOLOGY

Kirumbi (2018) defined research design as the set of methods and procedures used in collecting and analyzing measures of the variables specified in the research problem. A research design is a framework that has been created to find answers to research questions.

Two types of research designs are known they are the experimental and the quasi-experimental design. Under the experimental design, the elements are under the control of the researcher, while under the quasi-experimental designs; the various elements of the design are not under the control of the researcher. This study will adopt the quasi-experimental design. This is due to the fact that the element of design is human beings who are not under the direct control of the researcher. While this method will be used in this study, the cross-sectional survey will be adopted since it takes a snapshot of a situation and analyzes it. The survey instrument will be designed in such a way that meaningful results will be achieved.

Osikhotsali (2021), the population is the pool of individuals from which a statistical sample is drawn for a study. The target population for this study is a cross-section of employees of Lecturers of Federal University Otuoke who are ASUU members. According to the report from the office of the registrar, the academic staff of Federal University Otuoke is estimated to have a population of 462

Sampling is the process of selecting units (e.g. people, organisations) from a population of interests so that by studying the sample, a fairly generalized result is traceable back to the population from which they were chosen (Trochim, 2006).

According to the report from the office of the registrar, the academic staff of Federal University Otuoke is estimated to have a population of 462. This figure is however inaccessible therefore taro yamane formula would be used to calculate a reliable sample size. The formula is represented as;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

n = the sample size?

N = the population under study (462)

E = the margin error (0.05)

Thus;

Therefore,

$$N = 462$$

$$e = 0.05$$

Hence the sample size for this study is given by

$$n = \frac{462}{1 + 462(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{462}{1 + 462(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{462}{1 + 0.2125}$$

$$n = \frac{462}{1.2125}$$

$$n = 381$$

There are basically two sets of data in social science research; these are primary and secondary data source. Both sources were explored in this research. The secondary data was obtained from Literature on Corporate strategy on firm performance Journals and text books and articles on net. The primary source entails obtaining first hand information about the study subject through observation and questionnaire. The researcher will use the questionnaire method to obtain information without influencing the respondents for appropriateness, the questionnaire was given to the researchers colleagues and fellow entrepreneur for verification and this was further protested to ensure reliability and validity.

This study, examines the effect of corporate strategy on firm performance.

The independent variable is "Strike Action" The dimensions of the independent variable (Strike Action) are Economic strike, general strike wildcat strike. Adopted from Paul E. Spector (2000). The response format was based on an adjusted four-point Likert type scale ranging from (1) 'strongly disagree' to (5) 'strongly agree'.

Employee productivity which comprised of 3 items was adapted from (Martini 2012). The response format was based on an adjusted four-point Likert type scale ranging from (1) 'strongly disagree' to (4) 'strongly agree'.

Validity measures the extent to which the instrument is relevant to the study. To measure the true value of the variables for the individuals being measured, the researcher applied the content validity and construct validity to access the instrument. To measure the content validity experts in the field of management sciences validated our instruments.

Construct validity refers to how well you translated or transformed a concept, idea, or behaviour that is a construct into a functioning and operating reality, the operationalization. Most of the variables that were employed for this study were sourced from existing literature and had been pre-tested and validated in previous studies (Taherdoost, 2016). Therefore the variables had construct validity.

Reliability is the faith that one can have in the data obtained from the use of an instrument, that is, the degree to which any measuring tool controls for random error (Mohajan, 2017). Data are said to be reliable if they are consistent, accurate and precise, therefore Scale reliability will be calculated using Cronbach Alpha. It is the most appropriate statistical test for reliability given the nature of response to be used to construct the scales. Using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS).

Bryman & Bell (2003) an Alpha coefficient of 0.80 is generally accepted as a good level of internal reliability of the instrument, though an Alpha level of 0.7 is also considered to be efficient.

Data analysis could be defined as the processing of data to search for trends and relationship to provide explanations as bases for inference and conclusions, and state implications. A multi-step systematic content-analysis procedures, as well as basic descriptive statistical procedure, will be used to analyze the data obtained in this study.

To empirically evaluate the relationship between strike action and employee productivity, the multiple regression analysis will be employed using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). The multiple regression analysis was chosen because all the variables in the study are measured in ordinal scale. The analysis considered the relationship between the dimensions of strike action (economic strike, wildcat strike, general strike) and measures of employee productivity is (employee commitment).

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

In this chapter data collected and its analysis are reported, also the findings of this study were discussed.

Questionnaire Administration and Retrieval

: Summary of Response Rate

Questionnaire	Observation	Percentage
Numbers Issued	381	100
Numbers returned	360	94
Numbers lost	21	6

Source: Field Survey, (2026)

The above table shows the summary of the copies of questionnaire distributed and the number returned. A total number of 381 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to respondents and 360 copies were returned, constituting 94% response rate. These were found to be valid and useful for the analysis.

BIODATA OF THE RESPONDENTS

	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	210	58
	Female	150	42
	Total	360	100
Marital Status	Single	120	33
	Married	240	67
	Total	360	100
Age	18-25 years	-	
	26- 30 years		
	31- 35 years	10	3
	36 – 40 years	50	14
	41 -45 years	190	53
	Above 45 years	120	33
	Total	360	100
Highest Qualification	SSCE	-	-
	Hnd/Bsc		
	MSc	230	64
	PhD	130	36
	Total	360	100
Designation	Top Management	175	49
	Middle Management	120	33
	Lower Management	65	18
	Total	360	100
Work Experience	Less than 5 years	45	13
	6- 10 years	115	32
	11-15 years	135	38
	Above 15 years	65	18
	Total	360	100

Source Fieldwork 2026

From the results as shown in table 4.2, it was observed that the male gender dominates the organization with 210 respondents representing 58% and 150 female representing 42%. The marital status of the respondent indicates that 33% are single, 67% are married. The age bracket of shows that majority of the sampled respondent are 41-45 years which are 53%, 33% are above 45 years 14% are 36-40 years and 3% are 31-35 years. On the highest educational qualification of the sample, it was shown that 64% of the response were MSc holders, 36% are PhD. The position in the organisation shows that 49% of the respondent are top management, 33% of the respondent are middle management while 18% are lower management. The work experience based on sample shows that 38% of the respondent has experience ranging from 11 -15 years, closely followed by 32% of respondent who have experience 6-10 years 18% are above 15 years while 13% are below 5 years.

Descriptive Data Analysis**Respondent perception on the influence of Industrial Action and Employee Commitment**

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
General Strike						
The conditions of service in public universities has contributed to several strike actions				120	240	360 (100)
Inadequate funding in public universities lead to frequent strike actions.				80	280	360 (100)
The prolonged strike actions have affected student performance in public universities.				220	140	360 (100)
Incessant strike actions has drastically reduced quality of education in Nigeria tertiary institution				275	85	360 (100)
Wildcat Strike						
The manner in which employment relations issues and workers grievance have been handled led to strikes in public universities				70	290	360 (100)
Government failure to honor its agreement led to strike actions in public universities				115	245	360 (100)
Mismanagement of the economy by the government has led to massive strikes in public universities.				270	90	360 (100)
The inability of the government, university management and trade union leaders to negotiate during the collective bargaining has resulted in strikes in public universities.				250	110	360 (100)
Economic strike						
Wages/salaries paid to the employees in public universities led to several strike actions.				80	280	360 (100)
The implementation of the new pay policy (single payment platform) has resulted in strikes across the public universities.			30	190	140	360 (100)

Delay in payments of wages and other emoluments have contributed to strikes in the public universities.	30	50	70	150	60	360 (100)
Unnecessary interference in the tertiary institutions' affairs by government has led to several strikes in the universities.			10	50	300	360 (100)
Employee Productivity						
Distortion and disruptions of school calendar and academic activities affect productivity				290	70	360 (100)
Prolong strikes in the public universities have created conflict between management and employees			25	250	85	360 (100)
The strike actions by the employees have affected academic activities such as research and publications		30	15	175	45	360 (100)
The nationwide strike actions by the public universities has affected their productivity.				70	290	360 (100)

Source: Field Work, (2026)

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

In this section, the three hypotheses stated in the first chapter of this research were tested using the multiple regression through the use of SPSS software to determine the extent to which the independent variables influence the dependent variable in this study.

Regression Model Summary

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.889 ^a	.801	.791	.29675

a. Predictors: (Constant),

Source: SPSS Version 23

From the model summary above shows the Adjusted R squared is coefficient of determination which tells us the variation in the dependent variables due to change in the independent variables. From the findings in the above table the value of adjusted R squared is 0.809 and indicates that there was variation of 80.1% on employee productivity due to changes in general strike, wildcat strike and economic strike eat 95% confidence interval. This shows the significant that 80.1% of the variations in industrial action accounted for by the variations in the independent variables and the remaining 19% are accounted by other factors contained in the standard error

Multiple Regression of industrial action and employee productivity**Coefficients^a**

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1. (Constant)	5.216	.125		41.876	.000
General strike	.447	.166	.532	3.182	.000
Wildcat Strike	.383	.210	.681	5.182	.000
Economic strike	.467	.391	.653	4.078	.000

a. Dependent Variable: employee productivity

The table above showed the multiple regression analysis for the three variables of industrial strike. It was indicated that general strike has a positive effect on employee productivity ($\beta = 0.532$, $P < 0.000$). Wildcat strike has a positive effect on employee productivity ($\beta = 0.681$, $P < 0.000$). It was indicated that economic strike has a higher positive effect on employee productivity ($\beta = 0.653$, $P < 0.000$).

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between general strike and employee productivity

The first Hypothesis of no significant relationship between general strike and employee productivity was rejected given the probability of 0.00

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between wildcat strike and employee productivity

The second hypothesis of no significant relationship between wildcat strike and employee productivity was rejected given the probability of 0.00

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between economic strike and employee productivity

The third hypothesis of no significant relationship between economic strike and employee productivity was also rejected given the probability of 0.00.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study were discussed under the following sub headings;

General strike and employee productivity

Our hypothesis of no significant relationship between general strike and employee productivity has a positive coefficient of 0.532 and a probability value of 0.000. The findings reaffirmed the results of the previous studies that were conducted by researchers (Wills, 2014; Clotfelter *et al.*, 2010).

According to Wills (2014), the adverse effects of strike action in South African schools are obvious in terms of disruptions to teaching programmes. Wills (2014) found that in recent times effective teaching has been disrupted in most South African schools due to frequent strikes embarked upon by learners and staff. The author asserts that in the past few years the government considered declaring teaching an essential service due to massive strike action in almost all the universities in the country. The main reason behind this proposed policy was in fact to prevent disruption of teaching in most schools.

Clotfelter *et al.* (2010) also found strike action in schools affects academic activities including teaching. According to Clotfelter *et al.* (2010), evidence suggests that teaching has been disrupted in some schools worldwide over the past few years due to strike action.

Wildcat Strike and Employee Productivity

Our second hypothesis of no significant relationship between wildcat strike and employee productivity has a positive coefficient of 0.681 and a significant value of 0.000. The results of the study conformed to the results of previous researchers (Arputharaj & Gayatri, 2014; Gyamfi, 2011). According to Arputharaj and Gayatri (2014), strike action could bring about conflict which may affect the employment relations in the workplace. Arputharaj and Gayatri (2014) suggest that a strike is not a healthy tool in an organisation because it has the potential of affecting the employment relations between the parties (employees and employer). The authors are

of the view that each time employees embark on a strike, whether protected or unprotected, it shows some kind of betrayal. The consequence of this industrial action is that it damages the working relationship between the former and the latter.

Gyamfi (2011) also agrees with the above authors that strike action has a negative impact on the employment relations. Gyamfi (2011) found that any form of industrial action has a potential effect on the employment relationship in the organisation.

Economic Strike and Employee Productivity

Our third hypothesis of no significant relationship between economic strike and employee productivity shows a positive coefficient of 0.653 and a significant of 0.000. the findings of this study is an agreement with Usoro and Ogbuanya (2012) who discovered that incessant strike action in higher institutions of learning affect activities including research and publications. Usoro and Ogbuanya (2012) recommend that once there is strike action in the higher institution of learning it affects every activity, with research and publications as no exception. Usoro and Ogbuanya (2012) further add that once there is strike action it will give room for calendar adjustment which will inevitably affect the smooth running of the institution.

In his study, Olakunle (2011) also found that strike action affects not only teaching and learning but it also has major implications on research and publications. Olakunle (2011) contends that strike action has major implications on academic research in technical education. The author argues that academic research is an integral part of education due to the fact that it plays a crucial role in revamping and enhancing the quality of teaching and learning in technical education. According to Olakunle (2011), once there is strike action, students and researchers may not be willing to go into academic research.

Conclusions

The study concludes that, the financial measures of addressing strike action in Nigerian public universities include adequate wage and salaries, proper implementation of the new pay policy, restoring the old books and research allowances, adequate funding of the universities, improvement in working conditions and proper management of the economy by the government. The nonfinancial measures on the other hand include proactive management of employee grievances and disputes, fulfilment of promises or agreements by the government, good negotiation skills, collective bargaining or agreement, a conducive working environment and mutual respect.

The findings of also conclude that there are several consequences of strike action on both the universities and the country. With regards to universities, the impact of strike action is disruption of research and publications, low student performance, disruption of student learning, unhealthy employment relationship among the parties, disruption of effective teaching, and delay in students' graduation and disruption of the academic calendar. In Nigeria as a whole, the impact of Industrial action includes loss of investment, loss of employment or jobs, loss of government revenue, injuries and loss of life due to violence, bad reputation or image, loss of productive hours, falling standard of education, cost implications and national security threat. From the above discussion, it can be seen that even though strike action is a right in Nigeria, the consequences are great on both the institutions and the country. In addition to the institutions and the country, it also affects the employees themselves and employers. It can therefore be concluded based on the findings that industrial action does not only affect the institutions and the county but it also affects the employees (workers) and employers.

Recommendations

The findings of the study show that mutual respect among the parties is a key strategy of addressing strike action not only in public universities but all organisations in the country. Therefore, it can be recommended that the parties involved in employment relations must respect each other's views in order to avoid disputes that might lead to strike action.

The findings revealed that collective bargaining is an alternative to strike action. Thus, a good collective bargaining process helps prevent strike action in the workplace through consensus building. Therefore, the study recommends that the parties must explore collective bargaining as an alternative to strike action.

In addition to the above, the study found that failure by government to honour promises or agreement is a contributing factor to strike action in Nigeria. The study therefore recommends that the government must fulfil promises or agreements that were made in order to avoid or reduce strike action in universities.

The findings show that poor working conditions is a factor responsible for strike action in Nigerian public universities. This study recommends that the government must take active steps to ensure that the working conditions of the employees is improved in order to address strike action in the universities.

It was also found that funding constraints is a major cause of strike action in Nigeria public universities. Therefore, the study recommends that the government must allocate a substantial amount of money to the universities as funding. In addition to this, the researcher further recommends that the universities must also develop other mechanisms of generating funds namely: public private partnership, consultancy, running foreign programmes and other joint ventures.

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